

EDITORIAL DEPARTMENT

THE DEAF

**Their Education—Improvement of Conditions—
Responsibilities and Participation of the Profession.**

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The aim of this department of THE LARYNGOSCOPE will be to bring to the notice of its readers from month to month, facts that may be helpful to physician and patient in dealing with the life-problems involved in deafness. Suggestions from readers will be gladly received and all questions answered to the best of our ability.

Hard of Hearing Classes in London.

In every great city there can be found a certain number of children who are sufficiently deaf to be unable fully to benefit by the educational facilities offered in the elementary schools, but whose hearing is not impaired to an extent which would justify their inclusion in a school for the deaf. In classification, these children come, roughly speaking, midway between the slightly deaf, who can be educated in the front desks of hearing classes, and the very deaf, who require the special education of the deaf schools. As a useful general title, I prefer to speak of them as "hard-of-hearing" children.

Once I had begun medical work in the schools for the deaf under the London County Council, it did not take me long to realize that this class of children was neglected educationally, and that one of the most crying needs for reform lay in this direction. At that time they either dragged out a useless and colorless existence in the back row of a large hearing class, were put down as inattentive and left to themselves or wrongly punished, or they received—a few of them—education in a special school, either for the deaf or for the mentally defective.

*Extracts from an article entitled, "Hard-of-hearing Classes in London." Dr. Macleod Yearsley, *Volta Review*, February, 1915. It would be an excellent thing if classes similar to those established by Dr. Yearsley could be opened in all American cities.

The children fit for a hard-of-hearing class are not to be found among congenitally partially deaf cases nor from among those semi-deaf who have acquired the defect from such causes as meningitis, mumps, or injuries affecting the internal ear; this is obvious. Such cases have not usually sufficient hearing for any form of teaching but that provided in the deaf centers. It is essentially the middle-ear cases which are suited to hard-of-hearing classes, in whom deafness is due to suppuration or catarrh, especially those in whom it has been induced by adenoids. A few may show a limited amount of secondary involvement of the internal ear, but such condition is not common amongst those suitable for classification as hard-of-hearing. The children with middle-ear deafness are distinctly unfit for a deaf school and the necessary association there with deaf-mutes, so-called; whilst, at the same time, they are unable to profit by ordinary hearing-school methods. An analysis of the first 17 children dealt with gave the causation of the deafness thus:

1. Middle-ear catarrh	5
2. Middle-ear suppuration	9
3. Middle-ear suppuration on one side—catarrh on the other	3
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The primary cause in 12 cases was adenoids, or 75.8 per cent., a high percentage; but, when one takes into consideration the enormous potency of these growths for causing ear disease, not higher than is to be expected. Taking the five catarrhal cases, four were undoubtedly due to adenoids and one was doubtfully so. Of the nine suppurative, six were undoubtedly of adenoid origin; of the remaining three, one was due to scarlet fever; the other two gave no history. Three cases showed a combination of the two conditions, suppurative and catarrhal; on two of these the right and in one the left ear showed suppuration. The radical mastoid operation had been performed in three cases, in one of them on both sides.

The question of the hearing of these children was a very interesting one. In an experimental class of this kind it was a little difficult at first to fix the amount of hearing which should qualify for admission. Two of the cases who, at the initial examination at the head office, showed a hearing acuity, one of six inches for the voice and one for the raised voice only, were found subsequently to hear 48 inches and 120 inches in the one and 8 and 14 inches in the other. These children were transferred to the front desks of an elementary school and did well there. A third, who appeared to hear the raised voice 24 inches, it was found necessary to transfer to a school for the deaf.

I have found that several factors have to be taken into consideration in estimating accurately the fitness of a given case for the various forms of deaf education, such as shyness, individual variations in mentality, and the listlessness engendered by a sojourn in a large hearing class where the inability to hear has resulted in what may be termed chronic inattention. Deducting the three cases just mentioned and taking the amount of hearing in the remaining 14, the average hearing distance was about 16.3 inches in the right and 14.5 inches in the left ear, or for both ears 15.4 inches. In dealing with such small numbers, however, this would be a very fallacious figure upon which to base any conclusions. Subsequent investigations have shown me that it is of little or no use to form any empirical estimate of the amount of hearing which should qualify for a hard-of-hearing class. The amount of hearing which decides the question of whether a given child is to be classified as fit for (1) hearing class, (2) hearing class in front desk, (3) hard-of-hearing class, or (4) deaf school, can only be arrived at after prolonged experience and experiment. Careful examination by a skilled otologist is needed in every case, and the otologist has need to be one of experience in handling deaf children.

Probably, given normal mentality, a comparatively small amount of hearing is sufficient to enable a child with acquired deafness to be instructed in a hard-of-hearing class, whereas in dull or very backward children one is justified in advising such a class when the amount of hearing is comparatively great. In saying this, I am giving the opinion formed by some four years of close observation of hard-of-hearing classes and their results: thus I have found a bright, quick child, with only six inches of hearing for the ordinary voice, doing as well as, or even better than, a dull child, who could hear the same test at 16 feet.

Another important factor is the daily variation of the hearing of many of these cases. Whilst the hearing in some of the children remains to all intents and purposes stationary, that of others (especially in catarrhal cases) varies, within considerable limits, with the state of the weather and the health of the child.

I am inclined to think that the amount of hearing required to enable a child to respond well to education in the front desks of a hearing school is much greater than at first sight appears. It is characteristic of middle-ear deafness that the power of accommodating the ears to particular sounds is impaired, and that, in consequence, extraneous noises confuse the slightly deaf and hard-of-hearing scholar much more than the hearing child. In every class.

especially in large ones, there is a more or less continuous environment of outside sounds—shuffling, coughing, dropping of books, etc.—as well as the more distant hum of life outside the school, accentuated sometimes by open windows. If any hard and fast rule is to be made, the best plan probably would be to educate all those who cannot hear whispered speech below 6 feet (save, of course, the very deaf), partly in the front row of a hearing class, partly in a hard-of-hearing class. Lesser defects of hearing than the 6-foot whisper would do well in the front desks of a hearing class. The matter, however, requires further working out.

I would like to point out here that the whisper used in testing is made by emptying the chest of air and whispering with the last breath. Some persons appear to consider that a hoarse sound suggestive of the death-rattle of an elephant is what is meant by the "forced whisper." Fourteen cases had natural speech, but in almost every instance, unless educational measures had been taken to prevent it, it would have tended to become defective.

Before the class had been long in existence the increased industry and happiness of these children, the difference in their hearing, and the new confidence due to their finding a means of following the meaning of their teacher spoke volumes for its success. The class provided a method of education which enabled the hard-of-hearing children to lose their former apathy and listlessness, born of compulsory inattention from inability to follow their teachers in the hearing school. It enabled a number of them to return to a hearing class and keep up with their more fortunate classmates. It enabled those who had passed the school age to go out into the world with a ready means of communication, which was of enormous assistance to them in making a living.

In studying the results it was noted that, after deducting 4 children who had completed their legal period of education, 1 who died, 3 who left the neighborhood, and 71 still in the centers, 13 out of 27, or 48.1 per cent. were transferred to schools for the hearing, where they did well. Nine were, by reason either of the amount of their defect of hearing or speech, or because they were so backward as to require further special education, transferred to a center for deaf children.